

Scaling a Biological Simulator Platform to the Cloud

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PROJECT SPECIFICATION

The BioDynaMo project (<http://biodynamo.web.cern.ch/>) aims at building a general-purpose platform for large-scale biological simulation. Current work concentrates on developing a multi-threaded single server simulator. This step will be completed during the first half of 2017. However, the computational resources available on one server will not be sufficient to address ambitious research questions. Consequently, the next big step for BioDynaMo is the development of a distributed runtime.

In addition to high-performance clusters, BioDynaMo should be able to execute in a cloud environment. This has a strong effect on the design of the distributed runtime since cloud is an error-prone environment with high network latency and low throughput. Performance heterogeneity poses additional challenges for scheduling and load-balancing.

The student will improve her C++ programming skills, get familiar with modern software development practices, will learn about various challenges in distributed systems and how to solve them.

The duration of this project was 9 weeks, from *3 July 2017* until *1 September 2017*.

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ABSTRACT

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A distributed middleware early prototype has been designed for the *BioDynaMo* project, which aims to be a general platform for computer simulations of biological tissue dynamics. The middleware's functionality has been implemented keeping in mind the diversity of the performance and reliability characteristics of high-performance clusters and cloud environments. It currently, exposes a transparent and straightforward API to the simulation engine, hiding most of the internal low-level communication details, and it is also capable of sending *ROOT* objects over the network. By making use of a robust message-oriented library, called *ZeroMQ*, and by extending its flexible network node organization patterns, we believe it will be able to speed-up the execution of large-scale simulations when many computational nodes are employed. This claim, however, needs to be investigated using benchmarking and profiling techniques under real-world systems and network infrastructures.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The extensive use of computer simulation software in recent years has been a catalyst for improving scientific research especially in complex problems where deriving an analytical solution or using an experimental approach is not possible. Computer simulation software has been successfully used in many scientific domains (e.g., physics, chemistry, biology) to model various natural systems and processes, which helps researchers to explore and gain new insight on the system/process structure and behaviour. However, many laboratories or institutes working on computational biology, develop their own custom software to simulate a specialized biology process, which is a cumbersome, time-consuming, and repetitive process.

One of the CERN openlab's knowledge-sharing projects is *BioDynaMo*. It is part of *CERN openlab's* collaboration with *Intel* on code modernization, working on methods to ensure that scientific software makes full use of the computing potential offered by today's cutting-edge hardware technologies. It is a joint effort between CERN, *Newcastle University*, *Innopolis University*, and *Kazan Federal University* to design and implement a general platform for computer simulations of biological tissue dynamics, such as brain development. It aims at closing the gap between very high-specialized biology applications and ultimate giving researchers access to a user-friendly and efficient platform that can carry out large-scale simulations in the cloud.

The project focuses initially on the area of brain tissue simulation, drawing inspiration from existing, but low-performance software frameworks. Lukas Breitwieser started the project by porting the algorithms from the *Cx3D* brain simulation framework to C++ to exploit further modern processor architectures [1]. The next year, Ahmad Hesam added data persistency support to the simulation engine, so that it will be resilient against system failures, using the *ROOT I/O* framework [2]. Currently, *BioDynaMo* has a solid and highly optimized codebase which also uses *OpenMP* framework for easy parallelization of the simulation across multi-core systems. Furthermore, there has been some work in progress for integrating with the *ParaView* open-source software, which can provide in-situ visualization capabilities of the whole simulation at runtime.

In order to be able to run large-scale simulations with possibly millions of simulation objects, more computational power is needed. For that purpose, a distributed runtime prototype is developed, capable of distributing the simulation work across many computing nodes, which are interconnected via an existing network infrastructure. The nodes can then independently execute their partial simulation and communicate with each other to share data, which are necessary for the simulation progress.

In this report, the design and the implementation of the distributed runtime prototype are described. In every section, the technical challenges and limitations are presented and discussed along with the chosen solution. The source code of the distributed runtime prototype can be found at the *BioDynaMo Github* repository [3], under the *distribution* branch. It is expected to be merged into the *master* branch in the future.

2. DISTRIBUTION ARCHITECTURE

Before diving into the details of the distributed runtime implementation, it is necessary to examine the basics of *BioDynaMo*. This section will provide an overview of how *BioDynaMo* models and performs the simulations and how these can be executed in parallel on many separate nodes.

a. Simulation Model

BioDynaMo simulates biological processes (e.g., cell proliferation, neurite growth) which take place in biological tissues. These tissues are modeled as a system of interacting cells, which are mostly affected by their microenvironment. More precisely, each cell influences and reacts to its neighboring cells within a specified radius. The user can specify the value of the radius before initiating the simulation. Furthermore, *BioDynaMo* supports multiple kinds of interactions (e.g., physical, biological) between the same pair of cells. The user can specify the logic of these interactions by defining custom subroutines. These subroutines, among other internal functions, are executed at each simulation step changing the properties (e.g., position, density) of the cells.

When a single machine cannot handle the simulation workload, the cells can be partitioned into multiple nodes, based on their position. A simple way to achieve this is by creating vertical slices in the 3D-space. These slices divide the (simulation) space into multiple non-overlapping regions. Each cell then lies in exactly one of these regions. If this step is performed correctly, each region will have approximately the same number of cells. Depending on the number of the computing nodes, one or more neighboring regions are assigned to each node. This way, each node simulations only a subset of the whole simulation. Effectively, all the nodes together simulate the entire biological tissue.

Before moving further, there is a significant issue that needs to be addressed. *BioDynaMo* models the simulation space as a continuous memory region that is stored on a single machine/location. With this configuration, it is trivial to compute all the interactions between the cell pairs. However, this is not the case when dealing with multiple nodes, as each node stores only a subset of the whole simulation space. Thus, there is a need for a special mechanism that will enable the exchange of cells (and their properties) between nodes. This mechanism must send the cells over an (unreliable) network, as the nodes involved may be located in the grid or in the cloud. Fortunately, the cell interactions can only be present between neighboring slices, and thus “adjacent” nodes. This restriction significantly reduces the coupling among the nodes, as every node will exchange data with at most two other nodes/neighbors.

To better understand the issue, [Figure 1](#) demonstrates a possible cell partition between two nodes. The partition in this example is performed using a vertical splice (line) in the 2D-space for clarity. The cells are indicated by black dots. In this example, the cells are split in such a way that the two nodes have approximately the same number of cells. Node L is responsible for the space P_L and node R for the space P_R . The maximum allowed distance for cell-to-cell interaction (radius) is equal to $d = S/2$. This distance d also defines the “hallo regions” for P_L and P_R spaces, which are marked with grey. At each simulation step, “adjacent” nodes must exchange the cells inside their *halo regions*, so each node's partial simulation can proceed to the next step.

Figure 1. Example of cells partition between two nodes

b. Node Communication Schema

By looking at the simulation process, it looks reasonable to use the **Master-Worker** communication model instead of a Peer-to-Peer (P2P) model. At first, the existing HPC systems and the cloud infrastructures can be programmed effortlessly, as the majority of them use a coordinator node, which manages the pool of workers/nodes via network communication. Furthermore, it is possible to scale our computations to many more nodes and greatly decrease the implementation complexity for the worker nodes. One drawback is the existence of a single point of failure (*master* node), but this can be solved by adding a *standby* master node that takes over in case of failure.

In the *BioDynaMo* case, the above mechanism can be exploited in the following manner: firstly, the *master* node partitions the simulation space and then sends the appropriate cell regions to the workers. Moreover, it keeps track of the simulation progress and continuously monitors the health of the workers. On the other hand, the *workers* are responsible solely for carrying out the actual computation of their partial simulation. This task also includes the coordination with the “adjacent” nodes using the **cell exchange mechanism**, which was described previously. The full functionality of this mechanism still needs to be implemented.

There are two ways for the worker nodes to implement the cell exchange mechanism. One way is that every worker node sends its halo regions to the master node, which will then propagate these regions to the correct recipients. This method provides transparency to the workers, as they do not need to be aware of other nodes (including their neighbors). However, the master node will soon become a network congestion point, as the number of nodes or the size of the halo regions increase.

The other way is that every worker node explicitly connects to its neighbor(s) and exchange cell data through this connection. Even though this method involves more coding effort, it scales much better when it comes to a large number of worker nodes. [Figure 2](#) illustrates the extended Master-Worker schema. It is evident that both the first and the last worker connect only to a single neighbor.

Figure 2. Master-worker schema with worker-worker connection

c. Runtime prototype requirements

BioDynaMo's end goal is to support the distributed execution of the simulation on both clusters and hybrid cloud infrastructures. These environments are very different in terms of performance, reliability, node management and application's execution model. Therefore, the distributed runtime prototype has to be as flexible, modular and efficient as possible in both environments. Some of the most essential desired requirements for this prototype are highlighted below:

- **Low network latency**, as the "adjacent" nodes regularly exchange data
- **High throughput**, as the "halo regions" may contain lots of points, requiring a lot of memory
- **Broker & peer-to-peer communication**, for the master-worker and worker-worker communication
- **Fault-tolerant** to network and system failures with **recovery support**
- Written in C or C++, to **integrate** quickly with the current implementation

In HPC clusters, *MPI* is dominant. Taking advantage of the *tightly-coupled* nodes, *MPI* provides total control over the transmitted low-level data, mechanisms for managing and launching new jobs and fast communication. However, the lack of fault-tolerance is a significant issue. More specifically, current *MPI* implementations seem to not be able to recover, from transient network failures, resulting in the crash of the whole application [4]. Moreover, *MPI* does not support the dynamic node addition/removal while the application is running. Both of these drawbacks indicate that *MPI* is not well suited for our needs since especially the cloud infrastructures tend to be error-prone.

Another approach is to use a messaging library that will abstract the data transfers over the network and act as a *message-oriented middleware* (MOM). Ideally, such library/framework must be able to deliver reliably and efficiently the messages over an unreliable dynamic network. Many options are available including the popular ones *RabbitMQ*, *Apache Kafka*, *Apache ActiveMQ* and *ZeroMQ*, each one having its own specific uses, advantages, and disadvantages.

Both *Kafka* and *ActiveMQ* require the *Java Runtime Environment*, which introduces an unacceptable overhead, while *RabbitMQ* is not flexible enough to support our network architecture. Thus, for this project, *ZeroMQ* was chosen. *ZeroMQ* is able to cope with the aforementioned *MPI* drawbacks. *ZeroMQ* can queue the outgoing packets internally until the receiver that experienced failure restarts, and it can be used to inform the master node for the arrival or departure of a node, at the network protocol level.

3. ZeroMQ

ZeroMQ (or \emptyset MQ/ZMQ) is a **high-level message-passing** library that provides high-speed asynchronous I/O, atomic delivery of messages in FIFO order and flexible messaging patterns. The asynchronous I/O enables the **computation-communication overlap**, effectively reducing the communication overhead. Moreover, *ZeroMQ* provides fault-tolerance on low-level networking errors, so the programming can focus on the implementation of the actual architecture and protocol, rather than dealing with raw TCP sockets. However, it does not provide an application end-to-end message delivery guarantee. Typically, dealing with this issue requires the adoption of a **retransmission mechanism**, using *timeouts* and *acknowledgments* at the application layer.

This section introduces the basics of the *ZeroMQ* framework, emphasizing on specific parts needed to the reader, to fully understand the implementation of the runtime prototype. A much more detailed guide is available at the *ZeroMQ* website [5].

a. ZeroMQ's Sockets API

ZeroMQ exposes an API similar to the famous *Berkeley Sockets* API, commonly used in many low-level networking libraries. However, *ZeroMQ*'s function calls are much more powerful and hide many internal details of the message-processing engine. By using *ZeroMQ*'s simple API, it is possible to build complicated architectures using the widely known notion of sockets and messages.

Before the programmer can create and use sockets, it is mandatory to initialize a context. This context is a pre-processing step for the *ZeroMQ* framework. To create a new context `zmq_ctx_new()` is used. Note that a single context should be created for each process. The reader is encouraged to read about the available socket types at the *ZeroMQ* guide before proceeding to the rest of this section.

The creation and the deletion of a socket is performed using `zmq_socket()` and `zmq_close()` function calls. Configuring a socket by setting or reading/checking an option is done using `zmq_setsockopt()` and `zmq_getsockopt()`. The `zmq_bind()` and `zmq_connect()` functions are used to plug a socket into the network. Finally, to send a message through a socket and receive one from it, the programmer can use the `zmq_msg_send()`, and `zmq_msg_recv()` functions. Finally, when dealing with multiple sockets, the thread can do polling, using the `zmq_poll()` function to wait for a message on multiple endpoints.

ZeroMQ's sockets use raw sockets underneath. The type of the raw socket depends on the transport defined when creating the socket. Multiple unicast (i.e., `tcp`, `ipc`, `inproc`) and multicast (i.e., `epgm`, `pgm`) transports are available. Two special transports support communication between processes (`ipc`) and between threads (`inproc`). These "sockets" can be used for synchronization purposes.

b. Messaging Patterns

ZeroMQ's flexibility originates from the different messaging patterns that cover a wide area of applications. These hard-coded patterns provide the intelligence in the *ZeroMQ*, as they define multiple ways of distributing data/work/jobs. Each pattern is implemented using a pair of sockets, which will be explained later on. The built-in core *ZeroMQ* patterns are:

- **Request-reply**, which connects a set of clients to a set of services. This is a remote procedure call and task distribution pattern.
- **Pub-sub**, which connects a set of publishers to a set of subscribers. This is a data distribution pattern.
- **Pipeline**, which connects nodes in a fan-out/fan-in pattern that can have multiple steps and loops. This is a parallel task distribution and collection pattern.

- **Exclusive pair**, which connects two sockets exclusively. This is a pattern for connecting two threads in a process, not to be confused with "normal" pairs of sockets.

For this runtime prototype, the *request-reply pattern* is used for both *master-worker* and *worker-worker* communication. Even though the pipeline pattern may seem more suited for distributing the data to the workers, it does not provide any built-in mechanism for sending packet delivery acknowledgments back to the master node. The same holds true for the pub-sub pattern, which could be used for multicasting control messages from the master node. The *exclusive pair pattern* is also used for coordinating threads in the implementation of the worker node API.

c. Routing Messages

A primary difference between raw sockets and *ZeroMQ's* ones is that the latter can have many outgoing and many incoming connections. That means that a ZMQ socket can receive a message from multiple endpoints and can send a message to a specific endpoint/address. In both cases, the address is originated from the set/group of the connected (to the one we want to send/receive) sockets. That means that there must be a way to manage these addresses, in such a way that the sender can specify the desired recipient and the receiver is able to find the sender. This mechanism is called reply message envelopes.

So in short, the request-reply pattern makes use of envelopes to combine the message payload with the reply address/endpoint in a single entity, called *ZeroMQ message*. Each *ZeroMQ's* message is a list/array of zero or more frames, each one of these is a single string. These frames are used to separate the components of a message (for example the message header from the body). Therefore, formally the ZeroMQ reply envelope consists of zero or more reply addresses, followed by an empty frame (the envelope delimiter), followed by the message body (zero or more frames).

In [Figure 3](#), the structure of a simple "Hello" message destined to the socket with address/identity "ABC" is shown. Typically, socket's identities are binary strings that are automatically generated during socket's connection procedure. More specifically, they are set by a *ROUTER* socket when a *REQ* or *DEALER* socket attempts to connect. However, they can be modified afterward to a user-defined value.

Figure 3. Structure of a ZeroMQ message with reply envelope

A *REQ* socket is used to send synchronous requests (i.e., cannot send two requests in a row without having received first a reply) while a *DEALER* socket to send asynchronous ones. It is time to focus on a specific socket combination, which will be used thoroughly in the prototype implementation. That is the *ROUTER-DEALER* combination. Using this combination asynchronous clients (i.e., *DEALERS*) are talking to asynchronous servers (i.e., *ROUTERS*), where both sides have full control over the message formats. The *ROUTER* socket, unlike other sockets, tracks every connection it has and tells the caller about these. Quoted from the *ZeroMQ* guide:

When receiving messages, a ZMQ_ROUTER socket shall prepend a message part containing the identity of the originating peer to the message before passing it to the application. When sending messages a ZMQ_ROUTER socket shall remove the first part of the message and use it to determine the identity of the peer the message shall be routed to.

Therefore, when sending a message from a *ROUTER* socket, the first frame of the message must be the identity of the socket to which the message is destined. This way, the *ROUTER* socket is able to propagate the message to the correct connection (i.e., raw socket).

d. The Majordomo Pattern

Majordomo is one of the reliable request-reply patterns described in depth in the *ZeroMQ* guide. It provides a service-oriented queuing mechanism, where a set of clients can send messages to a set of workers. Each worker can register to one or more services, to indicate that it can serve particular requests. An intermediary broker (which can run on the *master* node) is responsible for handling the messages from either clients or workers. [Figure 4](#) illustrates this architecture as a message workflow diagram.

Because the broker is a vital component of the architecture, it has some extra responsibility. At first, it manages the connections to workers and clients, respectively. For that purpose, it uses a single *ROUTER* socket, which can send and receive messages from multiple clients and workers. Therefore, each client can send messages to a specific worker, using just the worker's unique identifier (i.e., service name) for routing. Using the same mechanism the worker can send a reply/report back to the client.

In addition to the routing mechanism, the broker makes use of a technique called *heartbeating*, to detect failures across the workers. The broker keeps track of active workers. Every few seconds it sends messages with no payload to each worker node. If the worker replies in a reasonable amount of time, it means that it is still alive and is capable of serving future requests. If it does not, the broker retries a few times, to minimize the possibility of a network-related issue. If there is still no answer, the broker assumes that the worker node is offline, and does the necessary clean-up actions.

Figure 1. The Majordomo pattern architecture

e. ZMQPP Library

The sample implementation of the *Majordomo* pattern is written in C99. Since the existing *BioDynaMo*'s codebase is written in modern C++14, a port of this code had to be made. For that purpose, the *ZMQPP* library was used thoroughly.

The *ZMQPP* library provides high-level C++ bindings that hide most of the C-style *ZeroMQ* core interface. Also, it provides some useful additional features such as a *reactor* (pattern) class. The *Reactor* pattern helps to manage multiple sockets when a watched event occurs (e.g., a message heartbeat) by calling a user-defined event handler.

More details about the *ZMQPP* library can be found at Github [6], which contains the source code along with the installation and usage documentation.

4. RUNTIME IMPLEMENTATION

In this section, the distributed runtime prototype is described. This consists of the extension of the *Majordomo* pattern, the API definition for each component, and the actual implementation, based on this pattern. For each component, a technical explanation of their structure is presented. The problems that were faced along with their proposed solutions are also discussed when this seems appropriate.

a. Extended Majordomo Pattern

In the previous section, the *Majordomo* pattern was presented which describes the preferred way to organize the roles and the communication between the computing nodes involved. Even though this pattern is a solid foundation on how the distributed runtime should look like, as it meets most of the mentioned above requirements, it does not cover the *worker-to-worker* communication. Therefore, the pattern needs to be extended to (transparently) support this kind of communication.

For that purpose, a *DEALER-ROUTER* socket pair is used between “neighboring” workers. By convention, the “right” worker creates a *ROUTER* socket and acts a server (i.e., binds to an IP address), and the “left” worker creates a *DEALER* socket and acts as a client (i.e., connects to this IP address). This way, neighboring workers can exchange their halo regions asynchronously. Note that a single *ZeroMQ* socket pair is enough for both sending and receiving data between two nodes, using a single network endpoint. [Figure 5](#) illustrates the additions made to the *Majordomo* pattern, ignoring the client part.

Figure 5. Extended Majordomo pattern diagram (broker-workers part)

b. Client Implementation

As described in the architecture, a client is supposed to be a node that can send requests/jobs to the workers, receive replies/reports from them and query the broker node for specific information. In *BioDynaMo*'s case, a client can be considered as the communication interface with the broker/master node, which manages the distributed execution of the simulation. It can run on the same node too, as a separate process. In that sense, the broker acts as a **proxy server**, which just serves the requests coming from the clients to the workers.

As a proof-of-concept, a very simple `Client` class has been implemented. Using the synchronous request-reply mechanism in the spirit of *Remote Procedure Calls* (RPC), the client can communicate with the broker

and the workers (through the broker). Specifically, the client sends the desired command to the broker using a *DEALER* socket and then waits for a reply from the broker. The latter responds with ACK if the request was executed/served successfully or NACK in any other case. It is possible to send multiple commands (asynchronously) before starting to handle the responses on the client's side, though not recommended at this point, due to implementation limitations (i.e., the client has no way of knowing which request, a single reply addresses). Lifting this limitation requires the use of unique request identifiers.

Listing 1 lists the `Client` class API:

```
new Client (zmq_context, identity, broker_endpoint, logging_level);
SendToWorker (message, worker_identity);
Receive (msg_out, command_out, from);
CheckWorker (worker_identity);
RequestBrokerTermination();
```

Listing 1 Client class API methods

Initially, the application creates a new `Client` class, which will try to connect to the broker. The application also passes the *ZeroMQ* context object and a unique client identifier (string), which is used by the broker to propagate the reply/report back to the correct client. The application can then send a message to a specific worker, by providing its unique identification. The current implementation can also check if a worker is alive and can request the broker's graceful termination.

Right now, the client is primarily used to test and verify the correctness of the runtime, by initiating the communication chain in the test suites. In the future, it can be used to send the simulation job details to the broker, which in turn will start and handle the rest of the simulation. It can also request saving a distributed snapshot of the simulation or revert to a saved one. Also, it will query the broker node for information regarding the simulation itself (e.g., completion percent, number of cells, visualization screenshots) or network-related statistics about the "health" status of the remote workers.

c. Broker Implementation

The broker is one of the most important parts of this architecture, as it acts as a proxy between the clients and the workers. In *BioDynaMo*'s case, the client along with the broker can be seen as the master/broker node. The broker role is to serve consistently requests coming from both sides. For that purpose, it creates two *ROUTER* sockets; one to talk with the clients, and one to talk with the workers. It then polls these sockets for incoming messages and handles them accordingly. The routing between the broker and the workers (clients) is done by appending the unique identifications into the message envelope, before sending the message.

The broker is also monitoring the health of the workers, using *heartbeating*. To do so, it first keeps a list entry for each connected worker. Then it asks for each worker node to periodically (typically every few seconds) send a HEARTBEAT message to the broker. If the broker misses a few messages from a specific worker, it eventually removes this worker from that list.

Because the number of the worker nodes can be quite large, the worker deletion (or "purging phase") is implemented efficiently. Each worker is being kept in an `std::set` using as a key, its id. The order is specified using the time of last HEARTBEAT message received from that worker plus some extra seconds, during those the broker expects to listen from the worker again. During the purging phase, the broker iterates this set and removes all the workers that have expired. It stops the iteration once it finds a timestamp in the future. This way, it does not need to check every single connected worker.

Listing 2 presents the currently implemented behavior of the broker depending on the type of command it receives either from a client or from a worker. In the future, actions must be taken if a node goes offline during the simulation execution, such as replacing the failed worker and eventually reversing the worker nodes to a previous simulation snapshot. Furthermore, the heartbeating mechanism can be improved, by gathering real-time network statistics (e.g., packet round-trip time) and dynamically deciding how often a worker node should send HEARTBEAT packets.

```

void HandleMessageFromWorker (message)
    switch (message type)
        case Ready:
            Add this worker to the workers list
        case Report:
            Send the report to the correct client
        case Heartbeat:
            Update worker's expiration time
        case Disconnect:
            Remove worker from the workers list
        default:
            Ignore message

void HandleMessageFromClient (message)
    if (message destination is the broker)
        switch (message type)
            case CheckWorker
                Reply ACK if the worker exists; NACK otherwise
            case BrokerTerminate
                Gracefully terminate the broker

    else if (message destination is some worker)
        Send the message to this worker, if the worker exists

```

Listing 2 Broker's execution logic

d. Worker Implementation

The worker nodes are the ones that carry out the actual computation of the simulation. Each worker node communicates with its “neighboring” worker nodes and the broker node. However, they exchange different kinds of data. The broker mostly sends control messages (e.g., heartbeats), except the partitioned simulation space at the very beginning. The current implementation supports the exchange of ROOT objects, inside messages that are sent over the network. Future work includes the failure detection of a worker, by its neighbors. This will improve the system's recovery time.

Therefore, the worker middleware needs to support the communication to both broker and (left & right) workers, and ideally under the same interface/API. Furthermore, it should store internally some message types, which need to be delivered to the application, and, at the same time, handle the control messages (e.g., heartbeats, handshakes) transparently, without the application intervention. That is one reason the worker's API implementation is more sophisticated than the broker's or the client's.

Figure 6 illustrates the main components of the middleware's implementation. One will first notice the two dashed yellow lines. These lines represent two threads, namely the application and the network thread. The *application thread* is the one that calls the API methods. The *network thread* is a separate thread that is spawned by the middleware and deals with all the network communication tasks. These include sending a packet using a socket, listening to the registered sockets for incoming messages, storing a message destined for the application and handling low-level control messages and processes, such as heartbeating and handshaking.

Figure 6. Breakdown of the worker's middleware implementation

The following paragraphs describe the elements of this figure. At the very top, the middleware exposes a simple API to the application, which is used to setup this node's connections, start and stop accepting incoming messages, send and receive messages over the network and check the connection status to remote nodes. Since the application thread executes the API methods, it accesses the memory region where messages are buffered to or from the application. Therefore, it can enqueue or dequeue a message from the storage.

Listing 3 presents the full worker's middleware API. In order to initialize the API class, we pass the `zmq::context` object, which must be unique for every process, a unique id for this node (i.e., identity) and the logging level. The `Add*Communicator` methods are used for setting up the necessary for this node, connections. The endpoint argument is a string of the form "tcp://ip:port" or "tcp://hostname:port." The `*DebugMessage` methods are used for sending/receiving a simple string over the network. Even though they are mainly used for testing, they provide valuable insight on how to write more extensive and more complicated communication routines. The `SendHaloRegion` and `ReceiveHaloRegion` methods are the ones to use for exchanging halo data between two workers. Their generic implementation allows sending any ROOT object, once the object is serialized. The remaining methods of the API are `Start`, `Stop`, `IsConnected`, and `SetWaitingTimeout`, which are self-explanatory.


```

class DistWorkerAPI {
public:
    DistWorkerAPI(zmqpp::context* ctx, const std::string identity,
                  LoggingLevel level);
    ~DistWorkerAPI();

    bool Start();
    bool Stop(bool wait = true, bool force = false);

    void AddBrokerCommunicator(const std::string& endpoint);
    void AddLeftNeighbourCommunicator(const std::string& endpoint);
    void AddRightNeighbourCommunicator(const std::string& endpoint);

    void SendDebugMessage(const std::string& value, CommunicatorId to);

    bool ReceiveDebugMessage(std::string* value, CommunicatorId from);
    bool ReceiveDebugMessageFromAny(std::string* value, CommunicatorId* from);

    template <typename T>
    void SendHaloRegion(const T& region, CommunicatorId to, AppProtocolCmd cmd);

    template <typename T>
    bool ReceiveHaloRegion(std::unique_ptr<T>* region, CommunicatorId from, AppProtocolCmd* cmd);

    void SetWaitingTimeout(duration_ms_t timeout);
    bool IsConnected(const CommunicatorId comm);

    // ...
}

```

Listing 3 Worker Middleware node API

The need for two threads poses some additional issues concerning their coordination. One case is when the two threads access the message storage simultaneously. That is a case of a *race-condition* and can lead to undesirable side effects (e.g., losing a message). One typical solution is to serialize the order of thread accesses. For that purpose, two distinct *mutexes* are used (i.e., one for each delivery direction). A possibly better solution would be the use of lock-free data structures, but there is no built-in support for the C++ standard library yet.

Another case is when the application wants to send a message over the network, but the network thread sleeps while waiting for input from the network sockets. A *ZeroMQ PAIR* socket successfully resolves this problem. This “socket” acts as a pipe between the threads and thus supports the exchange of messages and signals between the threads involved, using the same *ZeroMQ* API. Furthermore, it exploits the shared memory address space to avoid copy operations (zero-copy). However, instead of transferring the message via the pipe, they are first **buffered** (in the storage) and then a signal, to the network thread, is sent via the pipe. Thus, the network thread picks up the signal and calls the appropriate send routine. This decision makes sense when the destination node is temporarily offline. In that case, the message is stored on the sender’s side and sent over when the destination node becomes online again.

At the center of the figure, the *ZeroMQ* reactor is located. The reactor class, provided by the *ZMQPP* library, implements the reactor pattern. The *reactor pattern* is an event-handling pattern for handling requests delivered concurrently by many inputs, using a single thread (i.e., in our case the network thread). The handler then demultiplexes these requests and calls the associated request handlers. In the figure, the blocking queue designates the temporary storage, where the new incoming requests are buffered. The event-loop then processes these requests synchronously (i.e., one by one), by calling the appropriate handling method (i.e., callback). The arrow pointing to the storage indicates the potentially enqueue/dequeue message operation before actually calling the request handler.

The inputs that are registered to the reactor are the application-network threads pair pipe and the network sockets that communicate with the broker and the worker(s). The request handler for the pipe is straightforward since it only receives a single signal (when a message should be sent over the network). However, the request handlers for the broker and the worker(s) can be complicated, because they handle multiple message types. They can also behave differently, as they use different communication protocols. Besides these handlers, the reactor class does not make active decisions among the registered sockets, as it blindly calls the correct callback.

For all these reasons, it is a good idea to define an interface for the *Reactor-Communicator* interaction. The Communicator interface abstracts the protocol handling mechanism, which is responsible for managing the low-level details of communications of a single endpoint/node. [Listing 4](#) shows the Communicator interface API. There are two implementations of this interface. The first is the *BrokerCommunicator* class, which handles the communication with the broker and the *WorkerCommunicator* class, which handles the communication to a neighboring worker.

```
class Communicator {
public:
    Communicator(DistSharedInfo* info, std::string endpoint,
                CommunicatorId comm_id);
    virtual ~Communicator() {}

    virtual void ReactorTimedOut() {}
    virtual void ReactorServedRequests() {}
    virtual void Connect() = 0;
    virtual void HandleOutgoingMessage(std::unique_ptr<zmqpp::message> msg) = 0;
    virtual void HandleIncomingMessages() = 0;

    virtual CommunicatorId GetCommunicationId();

    virtual zmqpp::socket* GetSocketPtr();
    virtual bool IsConnected();

    template <typename T>
    void SetSocketOption(const zmqpp::socket_option& option, const T& value);

    template <typename T>
    T GetSocketOption(const zmqpp::socket_option& option);

    template <typename T>
    void GetSocketOption(const zmqpp::socket_option& option, T* value);

    // ...
}
```

Listing 4 Communicator interface

The middleware uses the *Communicator** classes the following way:

- When the application sets up the connections to the remote nodes, it creates and initializes the correct instances of the Communicator interface implementations (i.e. *Broker** or *Worker**)
- Once the network thread is spawned (when the *Start* method is called), it calls the *Connect* method for all the created communicators. This step will initiate the handshake process. The reactor can check if the remote node is online by calling the *IsConnected* method.
- Each communicator's socket is registered to the reactor so that each time an incoming message is available, the *HandleIncomingMessages* method is called (callback).

- If the reactor is signaled from the application and wants to send a message, the communicator's `HandleOutgoingMessage` method is called, passing the message as an argument.
- After one or more successful requests served, the reactor calls the `ReactorServedRequests` method, on all active communicators. If the reactor timeouts, it will call the `ReactorTimedOut` method. These methods can be used to write some post-request logic.

The `BrokerCommunicator` and `WorkerCommunicator` share some functionality. For example, they both hold a socket object and use a simple request-reply handshake process. However, `BrokerCommunicator` also handles the heartbeating by sending the message each time the reactor times out. The `WorkerCommunicator`, on the other hand, implements some extra logic to support symmetric (left->right or right->left) communication.

e. Common Objects

Some parts in the implementation of the client, broker, and worker middleware are identical in terms of functionality. For example, the message protocol is the same across the two nodes that are communicating and thus the creation, serialization, and deserialization of the messengers sent over the network must be functionally equivalent. Another example is the `Logger` class that is used for debugging purposes. These parts are explained in details below.

i. Network Messages and Protocol

The `MessageUtil` class is used for *object marshaling*. It implements the two basic `Serialize` and `Deserialize` methods that given a serializable object will produce a stream of bytes and vice-versa. Moreover, it provides two more helper functions: `PushFrontObject`, that first serializes an object and then prepend the output to a message object, and `PopFrontObject` that pops and deserializes the first frame of a message. `MessageUtil` uses internally the ROOT I/O framework for the (de)serialization. Thus, the objects to be (de)serialized need to have the `ClassDef` statement inside their class definition, as described in the ROOT documentation [7].

Besides the same byte representation of the same object inside a message, which is secured by the ROOT, the messages also share the same structure. [Figure 7](#) illustrates the shared structure of the messages that are exchanged over the network. The first frame is the protocol version, which is a string. In general, different protocol version indicate changes in one or more components of the middleware implementation. The client-broker and broker-worker/worker-worker communication use different protocol versions in their exchanged messages. Currently, only the second frame (i.e., `MiddlewareMessageHeader`) differs between the two.

Figure 7. Message structure sent between two remote nodes

The second frame consists of a serialized `MiddlewareMessageHeader` object. This header is appended and removed by the communicators and contains network-related information along with the type/command of the message, which is used by the middleware internally. Because the clients and the workers handle different types of messages, they use different headers (i.e., `ClientMiddlewareMessageHeader` and `WorkerMiddlewareMessageHeader`). The third frame, which is a serialized `AppMessageHeader` object, may contain application-related information. Currently, it holds just the `command` of this message at the application level protocol. The remaining frames (i.e., *application frames*) are used in accordance with the application message header. The middleware will not modify those.

Figure 8 shows the currently available fields for the middleware and application headers. The middleware header splits in two different versions (one for the client and one for the worker). At this moment, the only difference between these two is the type of the command object. In the future, the application header is expected to be entirely modified as the integration with the simulation engine starts. The middleware header can be expanded with fields related to network statistics that will improve the communicators' behavior.

Figure 8. Message headers fields (arguments in closed brackets are optional)

ii. Logging Class

The `Logger` class is used for printing messages to standard output. It is a wrapper over the `ROOT` I/O logging module, which is defined in the `TError.h` `ROOT` header file. It also uses the notion of the logging level, which is used to decide at runtime which messages will be printed, depending on their level of severity. For example, if the programmer wants to suppress the debugging messages, it will set the logging level to a value higher than `DEBUG`. The logging levels values are specified in the `LoggingLevel` enumerator class.

The `Logger` class supports the following methods: `Print`, `Debug`, `Info`, `Warning`, `Error`, `Break`, `SysError` and `Fatal`. This order also defines the severity of the message, from least to more severe, except the `Print` method. When the `Print` method is called, the given message will be force printed, ignoring the logging level. The intuition behind this method is for the programmer to use a single class for logging/printing.

```

// `this.identity` and `msg.dest` are instances of std::string
// `msg.content` can be a serialized ROOT object

Logger.Info("Sending object from ", this.identity, " to ", msg.dest, ". Content: ", msg.content);
  
```

Listing 5 Logging message example

Listing 5 shows how a logger method is called. There is no limit to the number of input arguments. The programmer can also pass object arguments, if there is implemented the overloaded `<<` operator for the `std::ostream`. This way the string message format can be defined possibly using the fields of that object. Finally, each such message is printed atomically (i.e., message string is not split) in the standard output, when using multiple `Logger` classes by different threads.

5. TESTING

During the coding phase, it is necessary to test the distributed prototype implementation. For that purpose some test cases were developed, that emulate various message exchange scenarios. Each test runs in a single process and implements a different communication schema. At first, the test setups the connection between different components (i.e., client, broker, worker(s)) by spawning multiple threads that handle a specific component. More specifically, it spawns one thread for the client, one for the broker and on for each of the workers; the same way it would work in the real world.

Figure 9 illustrates these scenarios. An arrow designates that a message is sent between these nodes. The order in which the messages are sent is indicated with the arrow numbers. The monitor corresponds to a client, the “dashed” server to the broker and the server to a worker. Below, the scenarios are explained in details:

- **Client-Broker-Worker:** A message containing a string is sent from a single client to a single worker, as a request. When the worker receives the message, it sends it back to the client from where it came. This test checks the basic client-worker communication via the broker.
- **Broker-Worker-Worker:** A message containing a string is sent from a single client to one of the two workers (e.g., A and B) in a round-robin fashion. The broker decides to which worker it must propagate the message. This worker A then sends the message to worker B, to which it is connected as a neighbor. The worker B receives the messages and sends it back to its neighbor (a.k.a. worker A). Finally, the worker A sends the message back to the correct client. This complicated scenario tests every part of the current implementation.
- **Worker-Worker:** A message is ping-ponged between two neighboring workers. The message can be a simple string or a ROOT serialized object, which intends to represent the halo region. This simple test’s goal is to test the worker-worker communication and benchmark the overhead of the middleware implementation.

Figure 9. Distributed implementation testing scenarios

6. WORKFLOW EXAMPLES

This section presents two code examples of using the distributed prototype API to handle the communication between nodes. In the first example, a worker will send a “halo region” request to another worker. Then the other worker will reply, with its “halo region” represented as a class, serialized with the ROOT I/O framework. In the second example, a client will send a “Ping” string message to a specific worker via the broker, which as it was explained previously, acts as an intermediate among the clients and the workers. The worker will reply with a “Pong” string to the aforementioned client.

a. Request of Worker’s “Halo Region”

For the sake of this example, we suppose that each worker knows the endpoint address of its neighbor worker. It is possible to send such information using a control message from a client to each of these workers. Furthermore, the first worker opens a socket for accepting incoming connections at 192.168.1.11 and the second worker at 192.168.1.12. Both workers open the port 5500 for communication.

[Listing 6](#) shows the required code for this simple communication between two workers. The left side shows the code for the first worker, which does the request and the right side for the second worker, which replies.

<pre> // Initialize ZeroMQ context zmqqp::context ctx_; // Setup distributed API DistWorkerAPI api(ctx_, "Worker1", LoggingLevel::kDebug); api.AddRightNeighbourCommunicator("tcp://192.168.1.12:5500"); api.Start() // Sending request for halo region api.SendHaloRegion(NULL, CommunicatorId::kRightNeighbour, AppProtocolCmd::kRequestHaloRegion); // Receiving "halo region" from Worker2 // NOTE: Blocking call HaloRegion region_; bool success_ = api.ReceiveHaloRegion(&region_, CommunicatorId::kRightNeighbour, AppProtocolCmd::kReportHaloRegion); if (!success_) { // Retransmit at application level // ... } // Do something with "halo region" // ... </pre>	<pre> // Initialize ZeroMQ context zmqqp::context ctx_; // Setup distributed API DistWorkerAPI api(ctx_, "Worker2", LoggingLevel::kDebug); api.AddLeftNeighbourCommunicator("tcp://192.168.1.11:5500"); api.Start() // Wait for "halo region" request // NOTE: Blocking call region_; bool success_ = api.ReceiveHaloRegion(NULL, CommunicatorId::kLeftNeighbour, AppProtocolCmd::kRequestHaloRegion); if (!success_) { // Wait again ... } // Sending "halo region" HaloRegion region_ = SimulationEngine.GetHaloRegion(); api.SendHaloRegion(region_, CommunicatorId::kLeftNeighbour, AppProtocolCmd::kReportHaloRegion); // Continue simulation ... </pre>
--	---

Listing 6 Code example of worker-worker communication for requesting a “halo region”

In both cases, the middleware API takes as the first argument an instance of `zmq::context` object. The second argument is the string identity of this node (i.e., “Worker1” and “Worker2”). Right after, it is possible to define the desired connections to other nodes. It is not mandatory to define a broker communicator for this example, albeit useless not to define one in the actual production environment. Once the `Start` method is called, the handshake procedures will take place.

For this example, we use the `SendHaloRegion` and `ReceiveHaloRegion` methods, which send an instance of the `HaloRegion` class. It is worth noting that these methods can send any object as long as it is serializable by ROOT I/O. In order to enable a class object to be serialized `ClassDef` statement is used in the class definition as follows:

```
class HaloRegion {
    // ...

    ClassDef(HaloRegion, 1);
};
```

The use of these function in pairs in both workers achieve the desired functionality. The `ReceiveHaloRegion` method will return `false` in case of a timeout. In production code, it is imperative to retry because it may be the case of a transient network failure. Even though *ZeroMQ* will retransmit internally and fix minor failures, it is not certain that the application level protocol is designed to keep up with possible delays/disconnects.

Figure 10 illustrates the structure of the messages that are sent by the middleware over the network. Right next to the frames, the data members for each message header class are listed. Please note the different values for the sender/receiver data members in the `WorkerMiddlewareMessageHeader` class and for the `cmd` data member in both header classes.

Figure 10. Request and reply message structure

b. Client-Worker Communication

In this example, the client will send a simple string message to a specific worker, and the worker will reply to the client. Please note that neither the client nor the worker needs to know the other's location (i.e., IP address and port number). The only need is to know the location of the broker (i.e., *master* node), which is set to 192.168.1.10:5500. It is the broker's job to handle messages from both directions and delivering them to the correct recipient (i.e., client or worker). If the client wants to send a message to a specific worker, the identity of this worker is required as well.

[Listing 7](#) shows the code for the client, broker, and worker. The broker runs as a service/daemon. By calling the Run method, the thread is blocked until signaled by a client that requests its termination. In the client code, due to the lack of a dedicated wrapper method for sending a string, a `zmq::message` object is first created. The string is then appended at the end of this message. Then, the `SendToWorker` method is called which takes as an argument the identity of the worker (i.e., where to send the message). If this worker has not established a connection to the broker, the latter will respond negatively to the client delivery request.

The worker uses the same API methods as before, apart from the replacement of the `{Send, Receive}` `HaloRegion` methods with the `{Send, Receive}DebugMessage` ones which are used for managing strings, instead of objects.

[Figure 11](#) illustrates the messages that are sent over the network. One thing worth noting is protocol string (i.e., the content of the first frame) which is different for client and worker. The other interesting data members are the same as in the previous example.

<pre>// [Client] // Initialize zmqpp::context ctx_; Client client(ctx_, "Client1", "tcp://192.168.1.10:5500", LoggingLevel::kDebug); // Create string message std::unique_ptr<zmqpp::message> msg_; msg_>push_back("Ping"); // Send message client.SendToWorker(std::move(msg_), "Worker1"); // Receive message ClientProtocolCmd command_; std::unique_ptr<zmqpp::message> received_; if (!client.Recv(&received_, &command_)) { // Interrupted... } if (command_ == ClientProtocolCmd::kNak) { // Broker: worker does not exist } assert(*msg_ == "Pong");</pre>	<pre>// [Broker] // Initialize zmqpp::context ctx_; Broker broker(ctx_, "tcp://*:5500", LoggingLevel::kDebug); // Run until signaled broker.Run();</pre>
	<pre>// [Worker] // Setup middleware API zmqpp::context ctx_; DistWorkerAPI api(ctx_, "Worker1", LoggingLevel::kDebug); // Add connection to broker api.AddBrokerCommunicator("tcp://192.168.1.10:5500"); api.Start(); // Wait for message std::string str_; api.ReceiveDebugMessage(&str_, CommunicatorId::kBroker); assert(*str_ == "Ping"); // Send reply api.SendDebugMessage("Pong", CommunicatorId::kBroker);</pre>

Listing 7 Code example of client-worker communication via the broker

Figure 11. Request and reply message structure

7. References

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